

Ctenosaura melanosterna in captivity

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Ctenosaura melanosterna
male.

INTRODUCTION

Various species of Black Iguanas from the genus *Ctenosaura* are usually recognised. A couple of years ago Köhler mentioned 12 of them (KÖHLER, 1995). The species with the most pronounced dewlap of all is known from three isolated localities in Honduras and Guatemala. This moderately large lizard, *Ctenosaura palearis*, was observed in the valley of the Motagua in south-eastern Guatemala, in the basin of the Río Aguan in the North of Central Honduras and on the small islands of the Cayos Cochinos on the coast of Honduras.

Since the localities are isolated and separated from each other, it is necessary to study the animals from the different locations to observe possible variation. Two research groups did so and, independently of each other, demonstrated the same differences between the animals from the populations in Guatemala and Honduras. One group (KÖHLER & VESELÝ, 1996) did not consider the differences to be significant, at least not based on the number of animals they studied. The other group (BUCKLEY & AXTELL, 1997) studied more animals and demonstrated significant differences between the two groups of iguanas. Besides various morphological differences, the black markings on the breast of the animals from Honduras are the most striking feature as this character is lacking in almost all of the animals from Guatemala. It is therefore not surprising that the name *Ctenosaura melanosterna* was attributed to the former group.

Keeping *C. melanosterna* in captivity, called *C. palearis* in those days, was previously described in VAN DEN HEUVEL, 1997. Those observations are expanded on in this paper.

HISTORY OF THE ANIMALS

A couple of animals caught in Honduras produced two clutches of eggs, the first in August 1997 and the second in July 1998. This second clutch of 34 eggs resulted in 33 hatchlings from which I obtained six in March 1999. That is where the story begins. One animal was killed after three months in skirmishes with fellow inhabitants; the group was completed with another specimen from the same clutch.

At birth the animals measured on average 48 mm snout-vent-length, 126 mm total length and weighed 3 g.

HOUSING

Upon arrival the animals were divided into two groups of three, paying attention to a more or less homogenous distribution of the sizes of the animals. One group was housed in a 70x50x50 cm vivarium, furnished with living as well as artificial plants and provided with climbing facilities like branches and a polystyrene back wall covering. Lighting consisted of ordinary bulbs as well as a ZooMed Reptisun 5.0 UV-lamp (15 W). The vivarium was placed in a heated room so that air temperature fluctuated between 25-35°C. In the spot-lights temperature could reach more than 40°C. The animals could approach within a few centimetres of the UV-lamp.

The other housing was furnished in a comparable way. However, lighting consisted of a halogen lamp (12 V, 20 W) without protective glass.

Since that vivarium was placed in a less heated room, additional heating was necessary to maintain a similar temperature (a heating mat and porcelain radiator were used for this purpose). For security reasons the lizards could not approach within 30 cm of the halogen lamp.

Ctenosaura melanosterna male.

the season. An UV-lamp, type OSRAM Ultra-Vitalux is mounted and also directed onto the branches. That lamp is switched on for two hours every other day. The animals can approach up to 30 cm towards the UV-radiator and up to 50 cm towards the halogen lamp. For additional heating, a heating cable is incorporated into the concrete floor. Heat coming from below the lizards is not exactly natural, but due to the large radiation surface, is very effective. Temperature is regulated by means of this floor heating. If necessary the power of the halogen lamp is also changed (between 200-500 W) to fine-tune the temperature to maintain the air temperature to between 30-35°C during the day, and at least 25°C at night. Under direct radiation, the temperature can reach up to 45°C. Humidity is not regulated separately, but in principle spraying will occur every day. That means that in those periods that the floor heating is on for a considerable amount of time, sometimes even continuously, the housing will dry rather fast. Since there is no substrate present, the relative humidity will be much lower in those periods compared to summer when the floor heating is less often necessary.

FOOD

Black Iguanas, like their green relatives, are general vegetarians in nature. However it is probable that they, unlike *Iguana iguana*, will consume animal food more often, based on the way that they chase prey. In addition, I found *Ctenosaura similis* in Costa Rica to behave as an absolute opportunist, trying to catch almost anything that is consumable. From *C. melanosterna* or *C. palearis* no other observations in nature are known other than that they consume leaves and flowers without any further specification. Keeping experiences with Green Iguanas and other species of Black Iguanas in mind, I decided to present the animals with an almost exclusively vegetarian diet. It is remarkable that an explicit preference exists for leaves. In that sense the green leafy parts of paksoi are much more appreciated than the white parts. A standard diet will consist of dandelion, collard and turnip greens, Chinese cabbage, paksoi, watercress, rucola, endives and other suitable greens.

Flowers, notably yellow ones (dandelion and rapeseed) have an enormous attraction, but they are not very well consumed. After a few bites the usual fresh green stuffs are attacked again. Red flowers from *Hibiscus* are eaten but not as fanatically as they are by Green Iguanas.

The method of eating of *C. melanosterna* is midway between the quiet grinding that is characteristic of *Iguana* and the fierce, almost hunting-like style of *C. similis*.

I give the animals grasshoppers that they consume very enthusiastically. I consider it as a treat rather than a basic need. Since it is quite possible to offer foodstuff of sufficient variation, I do not think that it is necessary to add any calcium or vitamin supplement to their diet. The animals are fed daily and are allowed to eat nearly unlimited amounts, only the occasionally offered grasshopper is directed by hand. The animals are willing to feed equally well from a bowl placed on the ground or from one higher in the trees. They are exclusively directed by visual stimuli. If the food in e.g. a deep feeding bowl is not visible to them, they will not think of eating even if the bowl is in the usual place. If the floor heating is switched off so that the floor is cooler, the tendency to eat from the floor is diminished as well.

BEHAVIOUR AND DEVELOPMENT

Ctenosaura melanosterna pair.

The animals in the two housings developed equally fast, albeit variably within the groups. In both vivaria a certain dominance arose rather quickly. This was demonstrated by a continuous growth of some animals and retardation in growth of some of the others. That process accelerated because the bigger animals constantly came to eat first, chased away the other animals from the feeding area and claimed the hottest basking places. All animals ate well but the quantity (and the quality i.e. the type) probably was not the same for all. It is likely too that social pressure enhanced the growth retardation of some animals. Long lasting and heavy fights were never seen, but well aimed bites were regularly observed. One of those bites became fatal to one of the animals. I found it one morning with tooth prints on its belly. The group was

completed with another individual from the same nest of comparable size. I stopped attempting to relate the influence of the type of UV-lamp to speed of growth and other developmental characteristics as it became obvious that several uncontrollable variables were coming into play and that the groups of animals were too small.

The housings became strikingly too small to contain the animals any longer so that moving them became necessary. At an age of eight months, when they were moved, the animals differed significantly in size and weight. Total lengths ranged from 185 to 265 mm (average 240 mm), snout-vent lengths from 75 to 100 mm (average 91 mm) and weights from 11 to 43 g (average 30 g). As stated earlier, no attempts were made to relate these observations to the source of UV-light or any other housing condition. In the large vivarium the development of dominance continued although it is probably more accurate to speak of it as a hierarchy. The two biggest animals, males without any doubt, have the first choice in basking places as well as on the feeding bowl. It is remarkable that these two never bother each other, except for an occasional head bobbing. The relation towards the other animals is explicit, notably towards the two smallest animals (gender not yet clear, probably female). No heavy fights have taken place, but the gentlemen seem to take pleasure in grabbing the tail tips of these two, it sometimes looks as if they are swallowing a herring in the Dutch way. Both of the smaller lizards have lost their tail tips.

Ctenosaura melanosterna male.

circumstances are kept unchanged, the animals will definitely be less active and will eat less if the relative humidity is high, like in Dutch summers when the floor heating is switched off. However it can not be excluded that this change in behaviour is a result of the changed way of heating: exclusively in the natural way (from above) versus from below.

At an age of about one year, total lengths of the animals differed by approximately a factor of two, from 200 to 410 mm (average 312 mm), snout-vent lengths were 85 to 155 mm (average 127 mm) and weights 40 to 152 g (average 92 g). At an age of almost two years these differences were even more dramatic. Total lengths of the four animals with an intact tail were 548 mm on average (from 480 to 610 mm), snout-vent lengths (of all six animals) 208 mm on average (from 150 to 250 mm) and weights were 415 g on average (from 138 to 715 g).

It is clear that once a difference in growth is established, it will continue to progress without doubt because of hierarchical developments. Therefore it is no surprise that the two animals that could be identified as males were by far the biggest and heaviest. Hence size is a sex characteristic for animals of equal age; typical male properties are characterised by specific elements. The massive head, compared to the far slimmer one of the females, is remarkable even more because it is visible quite soon (within two years). Standard male characteristics are also present: higher dorsal spines, larger femoral glands and a broadened tail base. With regards to the development of their body characteristics and based upon experiences with other iguanas, it is feasible to guess that the animals have reached sexual maturity. However, sexual activity has not yet been observed, except for some head bobbing. Since the animals described here are closely related, it is preferable for them to mix with another bloodline.

SUMMARY: CTENOSAURA MELANOSTERNA IN CAPTIVITY

Black Iguanas from Honduras, formerly known under *Ctenosaura palearis*, have been renamed as *Ctenosaura melanosterna*. In addition to a previous publication on this form, the author describes for a period of two years how captive-bred animals behave in captivity. The territorial behaviour that is said to be characteristic of Ctenosaurs, turned out to be rather limited, providing that sufficient space is available. Several males can even be kept together without an unacceptable degree of aggression. However, social pressure is likely to be responsible for extreme differences in growth rate.

Attempts to judge the influence of various artificial sources of UV-light on the growth rate could not be implemented due to the interference of other factors, such as social repression. However, the animals grew equally well in the presence of a ZooMed UV-lamp as with halogen lamps.

In contrary to some other observations (BRAUN, 1993) the animals are not at all shy neither in the large nor in the small housings. Usually they can be approached or even touched without any fear. If it is getting too much they will quickly fly into the tubes. However, being very inquisitive, they will pop up again very soon.

Ctenosaura melanosterna is an explicit lover of heat and will carefully look for the best places. They actively search out the Ultra-Vitalux lamp that produces a lot of heat. When it occasionally is a bit less hot, but still very comfortable, the behaviour of the animals is immediately influenced. In contrast to Green Iguanas who often are stimulated by a rain shower or in general by higher humidity, these black iguanas seem to be hampered by it.

Even when temperature and other

Ctenosaura melanosterna hidden in a cork tube.

The animals developed well on a diet primarily consisting of leafy plants. The occasionally fed grasshoppers are appreciated, though animal feed does not seem to be essential for their well-being. My animals are not shy at all. After two years, a housing of 3x2 m surface area and 2.5 m height is provided for six animals that weigh between 138-715 g at a total length of 480-610 mm. Air temperature is 25-35°C and under spot-lights can reach more than 40°C. Many climbing and hiding facilities are available. Radiation with UV light (Ultra-Vitalux) occurs every other day for two hours.

LITERATURE

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